

**D2.1 User survey on
High Performance Computing Needs**

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1 Executive summary

This report presents the findings of Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Cloud (NAIC) project, which aims to build a robust AI/ML infrastructure in Norway. Funded by the Norwegian Research Council, the initiative focuses on democratizing access to High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources, enhancing AI research and education, and supporting innovation across academia and industry.

1.1 Key Objectives:

- Assess current and future HPC needs for AI/ML in Norway.
- Identify technical and non-technical barriers faced by users.
- Guide the development of NAIC infrastructure and training programs.

1.2 Methodology:

- **Two national surveys** conducted between 2023 and 2025, gathering 78 total responses.
- **Semi-structured interviews** with a cross-disciplinary set of researchers and professionals to contextualize and enrich survey data.

1.3 Main Findings:

1. Compute Resources:

- The primary bottleneck identified was limited access to powerful GPUs.
- Even where resources existed, they were often insufficient or difficult to use efficiently.
- Norway’s institutional compute capacity is significantly behind global leaders (1/174th of the compute power compared to the US’s Frontier super-computer).

2. User Demographics & Roles:

- Most respondents were academic users; a secondary survey improved industrial representation.

- Majority identified as technical end users; a smaller number were non-technical or infrastructure staff.

3. Usage Patterns & Needs:

- Python is the dominant programming language, followed by C++ and R.
- SSH and Jupyter are preferred interfaces for compute resource interaction.
- Users expressed a strong need for support in training stages of AI projects, followed by deployment and verification.

4. Storage Needs:

- Disparities exist in storage infrastructure across institutions.
- There are challenges with petabyte-scale data access, data security, and real-time streaming.
- Current solutions like UiO's TSD and NRIS's NIRD offer some support, but not uniformly across all institutions.

5. Training & Support:

- Strong demand for training on using compute systems and distributed learning.
- A need for better guidance, onboarding, and interdisciplinary collaboration was identified.

6. NAIC Recommendations:

- Develop a unified, user-friendly platform with both flexibility and ease of use.
- Scale compute infrastructure significantly to meet national and international demands.
- Improve access to secure, scalable, and fast storage systems.
- Expand training programs via workshops, courses, and the NAIC knowledge hub (WP3).

1.4 Conclusion:

The WP2 study reveals a strong need for scaling up and simplifying access to AI compute resources in Norway. While significant progress has been made, additional investment and coordinated development are crucial to ensuring that Norwegian researchers and developers can remain competitive in the global AI landscape.

2 Introduction

Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Cloud (NAIC) is a five year project with three year funding support from the Norwegian Research Council (Grant Number: 322336) to establish a powerful AI/ML infrastructure in Norway that will foster AI education, research, and innovation. NAIC provides access to High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources and support for researchers, PhD students, educators, entrepreneurs, startups, and Small and Midsize Enterprises (SMEs) who are interested in exploring AI methodologies and developing advanced AI models and algorithms. Furthermore, the project provides inclusive training programs and resources, accommodating both individuals new to AI seeking an introductory level of understanding and those looking for more advanced courses to leverage the infrastructure for specific tasks.

Over the course of five years, the NAIC will bring together leading experts in the field to establish an infrastructure that provides accessible, affordable, and easy-to-use resources for machine learning and deep learning. The consortium comprises a diverse group of partners, including UiO, NORA, NTNU, UiB, SIMULA, UiA, SINTEF, UiT, SIGMA2, and NORCE Research, all of whom are renowned leaders in their respective domains. By pooling their unique expertise and resources, the consortium forms a dynamic and collaborative team fully committed to propelling the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning in Norway.

2.1 Survey

The survey was conducted in two phases: the first in spring 2023 and the second in the winter of 2024/2025.

In May 2023, the University of Agder (UiA), as the lead institution for Work Package 2, partnered with the Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Research Consortium (NORA.ai) to launch a national survey assessing the computational needs of AI researchers and developers in Norway. The objective was to collect data on the tools, libraries, and resources currently in use across diverse AI environments, identify key bottlenecks, and anticipate future requirements. The survey was distributed through all partners of the Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC) and via NORA's newsletter mailing list, yielding 63 responses. The sample was predominantly academic, with approximately 75% of responses originating from universities and research institutions. The remaining 25% were distributed among the public sector, private industry, and start-ups.

Following the analysis of the initial results, feedback in winter 2024/2025 revealed a significant underrepresentation of industrial perspectives. In response, the survey was revised and reissued to address this imbalance. The updated version was again disseminated through NAIC channels and the NORA newsletter, resulting in an additional 15 responses. Although academic respondents continued to comprise the majority (approximately 50%), representation from the industrial sector increased to around 40%, indicating progress toward a more balanced stakeholder representation.

2.2 Interviews

To supplement the survey data, 7 respondents from the initial cohort of 63 were selected for semi-structured interviews. Participants were chosen to reflect a diverse cross-section of the AI and machine learning (ML) community, ensuring representation across sectors, disciplines, and levels of experience. The interviews aimed to deepen the understanding of the varying challenges, needs, and priorities within the field, thereby providing richer, more context-sensitive insights to complement the survey findings.

3 Survey

3.1 Overview

The questions in the survey were structured around the following topics: Respondent information; Available resources and provisioning; Access and user interface; Code and data management; Programming languages and libraries; Project and model management; and Questions related to the NAIC project. Most of the questions were formulated to include both current use and what the participant regarded as future needs.

3.1.1 Respondent information

The questions in this section were aimed at uncovering the role and affiliation of the participant, as well as their general familiarity with artificial intelligence. In order to keep the content of the questionnaire relevant to the participant, this information was used to adapt the following sections. The roles and their focus were described as: Non-technical end user (SaaS level): You prefer to use pre-built environments and tools to support your work. You are able to reuse existing code, and make the necessary changes in common programming languages. Technical end user (IaaS Level): You prefer to set up your own environment and install the tools you need yourself. You write your own code. Technical staff (Bare-metal level): You mainly administer the AI/ML/Compute resources at your institution. For participants choosing the SaaS level role, the questions asking for technical details were left out. For those who selected the IaaS level role, only the questions regarding orchestration and provisioning of hardware were left out. And for the Bare-metal role, some of the details regarding programming languages and libraries were left out.

3.1.2 Available resources and provisioning

This section covers questions regarding what hardware resources are currently available to the participants, and what they believe are the most important bottlenecks with regards to resources. Participants with the Bare-metal role were also asked about which provisioning solutions they use. The purpose of these questions was to get a better understanding of the availability and use of existing resources, as well as whether or not there are sufficient resources to cover the expected need in the near future.

3.1.3 Access and user interface

In order to provide an interface and a proper level of access, the survey needed to address how the participants currently access and interact with their compute resources, and what can be done to improve the experience. These questions aim to give a baseline for how users will expect to interact with a future AI/ML platform and what they will be authorized to perform.

3.1.4 Code and data management

Data and code are two central components in an AI/ML solution. This section queries how the participants currently manage this with regards to ingestion, storage, versioning, annotation, exploration and sharing. The answers received here will, in turn, provide valuable input to how these important components should be supported in a future platform.

3.1.5 Programming languages and libraries

To support various programming languages, libraries, and different versions of both, a high level of flexibility is required in how an AI/ML platform is provisioned and presented to end users. To assess the scope of this, the participants were asked which programming languages and libraries they currently use and what they expect to use in the near future.

3.1.6 Project and model management

At present, working with and developing AI/ML projects include more than data and code. The code must be optimized and experiments must be tracked. Models must be trained, deployed and maintained. Resources must be scheduled to run the different experiments and training. All these tasks and more, must be managed in some fashion. This section of the survey maps how the participants currently manage their projects and how they believe they should be managed.

3.1.7 Questions related to the NAIC project

Here, the survey attempts to gather the data needed to determine which parts of AI/ML projects NAIC should prioritize supporting

3.2 Results

Of the 63 respondents, 50 regarded themselves as technical end users, 10 as non-technical end users and 3 as technical staff. The distribution is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Role distribution of the respondents

As mentioned in the introduction, and shown in Figure 2, there was an unfortunate skew towards academia in the respondent population. There were 48 respondents from academia, 8 from the public sector, 5 from the industry and 2 from startup companies.

Most of the respondents have resources for AI/ML available at their institution. As shown in Figure 3, 94.2 percent have access to GPUs, and 88.5 percent have access to CPU. When asked if their work required specific hardware, 92.2 percent answered that they require GPUs and 72.5 percent that they require CPU. More detail is available in Figure 4. Digging deeper into the answers regarding required hardware resources. Out of the 36 extended answers given, NVIDIA GPUs are mentioned in 23 of the 36 answers, AMD GPUs are mentioned twice and any GPUs are mentioned 7 times. The remaining 4 have special requirement like IPUs and FPGAs While most respondents have resources available at their institution, many of them claim that the main bottlenecks they face is related to not having access to sufficient amounts of the required resources. Adequate quantities of sufficiently powerful GPUs are at the top of the wish list. Of the 53 answers to the question “*With regards to resources. What are*

Figure 2: The distribution in affiliation among the respondents

Figure 3: Available resources for AI/ML

the main bottlenecks?”, 39 of the replies are related to compute and GPUs, 6 believe the lack of skilled support is the main bottleneck, 4 are concerned with data quality and 4 with storage speed.

Usability and flexibility are often viewed as opposing goals, but to cater to the diverse groups which are the potential users of NAIC, the system will need both. As Figure 5 shows, just over half of the respondents believe they

Figure 4: Required resources for AI/ML

will need privileged user access in the future. Looking at the detailed answers show that this is mainly to adjust their environment to suit their needs. When

Figure 5: Current and needed user access level to compute resources

asked “*How do you interact with your AI/ML/Compute solution?*”, about three quarter of the respondents use and would prefer to continue to use a direct shell, like SSH, to interact with their AI/ML resources. In addition, about half are also comfortable with using Jupyter notebook as their interface. Figure 6 shows

the distribution and numbers.

Figure 6: Current and needed tools used to interact with the compute resources

Towards the end of the survey the question of “*Which stages in your project do you expect to need assistance from NAIC?*” came up, to which 79% of respondents said they would expect to require the help of NAIC at the training stage, while less than 50% responded they needed the help during testing and planning, and a little more than 50% said they needed help with deployment and verification as shown in Figure 7.

3.2.1 Interviews

After the survey was completed, the responses collected, and the data analyzed, the subsequent step in the study involved conducting interviews. These interviews have now been completed. Their purpose was to gather deeper insights and contextual information that were not captured through the survey, by asking more in-depth and targeted questions.

The general questions planned for the interviews were as follows:

- Please explain how you gather data
- Please explain how you label data
- Please explain how you prepare your data for training and testing
- How do you implement your AI algorithm, please give specifics

Figure 7: At which stage in your project do you expect to need assistance from NAIC

- What would be your ideal workflow for AI?
- Follow up to ideal workflow - If you had to choose which are most important?
- Describe the help you would want from NAIC
- What would you like to have included in the setup guide for the NAIC systems?
- If applicable, what cross-disciplinary support would you want?
- How much data is available for Norwegian/European NLP models?
- What is required to create new NLP models for Norwegian/European languages?
- What does your work revolve around
- If applicable, why do you use multiple ML libraries? (Keras/TF/Torch)
- How long does your algorithm normally take? (Describe your compute power, when training)
- Is it possible to speed up your training with distributed learning?

- Who can we contact to get details on the computing power available

An example of a specific interview included questions such as:

- What is your work?
- What is your current workflow?
- Also please tell us about the resources used for training and the time it takes data gathering, exploring, labelling, annotating, preparation, initial experiments/large scale training, deployment and maintenance
- What is your ideal workflow?
- Please explain the data that you have and how you gather and label more data?
- Why use multiple ML libraries?

Based on the topics reported by survey respondents, the goal was to interview individuals with diverse backgrounds and areas of expertise. An effort was made to include participants from both academia and industry.

The topics of the people we wished to interview were:

- BI Timeseries
- Genetics
- Vision
- 3D mapping using aerial images
- Comp Sci
- Medical
- BioInformatics
- Political science
- NLP
- Teaching
- Social Media Analysis

- Recommender
- Oil and Gas

The topics covered by these interviewees included:

- NLP
- Genetics
- Medicine
- Teaching
- Recommender
- Oil and Gas
- Medical

These interviews have added valuable qualitative depth to the survey results and provided a clearer picture of AI workflows, data practices, and infrastructural needs across different fields of application.

3.2.2 Interview results

The interviews tried to fill the missing information, this missing information reinforced the results of the survey; namely that largest issue was compute, less technical persons struggling to find out where and how to begin when implementing new algorithms, struggling with loading data, and the use of cloud infrastructure.

3.2.3 Urgent user needs

Access to compute was the largest issue, after which issues such as knowledge about how to use systems, or access to fast resources using distributed systems and more. The lack of access to or knowledge about implementating models was another large issue, with some struggling with not enough cross disciplinary support.

3.2.4 Storage needs

Storage solutions differ between institutions, which means each institution either has to create its own solution or rent a solution from another institute. In return, the institute that rents the solution cannot control the physical location of data. There are also issues with loading data, when the datasets scale to petabyte.

3.2.5 Training needs

The respondents seem to agree that training on using the compute resources correctly is important, which includes not only how to use the compute resources, but also how to scale to multi GPU or multi Server training.

3.2.6 Secondary survey results

Of the 15 new respondents, 66.7 percent regarded themselves as technical end users, 26.7 percent as non-technical end users and only 6.7 percent as technical staff. The distribution is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Role distribution of the respondents

As mentioned in the introduction, and shown in Figure 9, there was an better spread in the response population from the secondary survey. There were 46.7 percent respondents from academia, 40 percent from the industry sector, 6.7 percent from the startup companies, and 6.7 percent responded with other.

Most of the respondents have AI / ML resources available in their institution. As shown in Figure 10, 81.8 percent have access to GPUs, and 72.7 percent

Figure 9: The distribution in affiliation among the respondents

have access to CPUs. When asked if their work required specific hardware, 81.8

Figure 10: Available resources for AI/ML

percent answered that they require GPUs and 63.6 percent that they require CPU. More detail is available in Figure 11. Deeper in the answers regarding the required hardware resources. Although most of the respondents have resources available at their institution, many of them claim that the main bottlenecks they face are related to not having access to sufficient amounts of the required

Figure 11: Required resources for AI/ML

resources. Adequate quantities of sufficiently powerful GPUs are at the top of the wish list. Of the 15 answers to the question “*With regards to resources. What are the main bottlenecks?*”, half of the replies are related to compute and GPUs, thirty percent believe the lack of skilled support is the main bottleneck, 25 percent are concerned with data quality and a smaller assortment are concerned with current cloud solutions.

Usability and flexibility are often viewed as opposing goals, but to cater to the diverse groups which are the potential users of NAIC, the system will need both. As Figure 12 shows, just a little less than half of the respondents believe that they will need privileged user access in the future. Looking at the detailed answers, it shows that this is mainly to adjust their environment to suit their needs. When asked “*How do you interact with your AI/ML/Compute solution?*”, about half of the respondents use and would prefer to continue to use a direct shell, like SSH, to interact with their AI/ML resources. In addition, about forty percent are also comfortable with using Jupyter notebook as their interface. A big change in the responses from the secondary survey is the increase in API-focused responses, growing to more than double the original amount. Figure 13 shows the distribution and numbers.

Toward the end of the survey the question of “*Which stages in your project do you expect to need assistance from NAIC?*” came up, to which 66.7 percent of the respondents said they would expect to require the help of NAIC at the

Figure 12: Current and needed user access level to compute resources

Figure 13: Current and needed tools used to interact with the compute resources

training stage, while less than 40 percent responded they needed the help during testing and planning, and a little more than 50 percent said they needed help with verification and a bit less with deployment as shown in Figure 14.

3.2.7 Summary

During last year, WP2 created a survey and interviewed a group of people.

Figure 14: At which stage in your project do you expect to need assistance from NAIC

The survey revealed a few different problems, the most major one being compute resources. This problem involves access to enough compute, how to use the compute, and how to scale the compute. In addition to the issue of compute, there was also the issue of knowing how to build large models and requests for some interdisciplinary support.

The majority of the users use Python and associated Python libraries for their AI, with another large portion using C++ and R there has to be support for using these with the NAIC system being developed, as this would cover most of the users.

With the survey having mostly academic respondents, the majority of those coming from UiO, there is a possibility for bias to be part of the survey. To fill the knowledge gaps from the survey, we also interviewed a group of people from different institutions, with diverse backgrounds. However, these interviews seemed to agree with the survey findings, adding some additional remarks about training on petabyte-scale datasets. Following the interviews, we applied a secondary survey to further close the gaps and rule out any bias. This round had a much higher percent of responses from the industry sector, as requested, but the majority of the problems were similar, if not the same, as the first survey.

The knowledge of how to implement and where to find the models to imple-

ment is addressed by WP3 through their knowledge hub. Workshops, courses, and digital seminars are to be held by WP3 to further strengthen the knowledge of NAIC and its partners. As for the compute, resources are currently being purchased, though there has to be an investigation into if the amount of resources being purchased in the project is enough.

3.3 Existing resources

3.3.1 Resource catalog

Each institution has their own separate compute currently, and with the GPU being the most important factor for AI, you can find the GPU's below:

NTNU

- 8x Nvidia V100 32GB
- 4x Nvidia V100 16GB
- 7x Nvidia P100 16GB
- 18x Nvidia A100 80GB
- 12x Nvidia A100 40GB
- 8x Nvidia H100 80GB

Or a total of 57 GPUs.

UiA

- 48x Nvidia H100 80GB
- 128x Nvidia V100 32GB
- 16x Nvidia P100 16GB
- 5x Nvidia A100 80GB
- 2x Nvidia T4 16GB

Or a total of 199 GPUs.

UiB

- 3x Nvidia V100 16GB
- 2x AMD MI100
- 6x Nvidia P40

or a total of 11 GPUs.

UiO

- 8x Nvidia V100 32GB
- 24x Nvidia A100 40GB
- 12x Nvidia 3090 24GB

Or a total of 44 GPUs.

UiT

- 16x Nvidia 2080ti
- 8x Nvidia 1080ti
- 4x Nvidia A6000
- 1x Nvidia 3090

Or a total of 29 GPUs.

Simga2

- 96x Nvidia A100
- 32x Nvidia P100

Or a total of 128 GPUs.

4 Compute

4.1 International Compute for AI

¹ In recent years, many countries have realized the vast benefits that AI can bring to the economic and social aspects of society. As a result there have been large investments in computing resources which allow for the development and deployment of AI. For the Norwegian Government's strategy on AI to be realized, large investments must be made to computing infrastructure, which in turn makes Norway competitive in AI. Investments to computing infrastructure would directly strike at the biggest problem according to the survey, namely access to compute.

Large compute resources are often divided into public, academic and industry sector systems, which the largest systems often being funded by different governments, such as in the United States, Canada and the EU. In recent years this investment into compute resources has vastly expanded, to meet the growing requirements for AI research and development.

4.1.1 United States

² ³ In the United States, Oak Ridge National Laboratory's frontier system boasts 1.679 Exaflops of peak performance, with another 200.79 Petaflops from Summit and 27 Petaflops from Titan. With frontier being the first system to reach exascale and is currently ranked number 1 on the top500 charts which ranks supercomputers.

4.1.2 Japan

Japan has both the worlds first large scale open AI Computing infrastructure, the AI Bridging Cloud Infrastructure (ABCI), run by the National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST). With the ABCI having a 37 Petaflops on their Compute Node(V) and 34.2 Teraflops on Compute Node(A). They also have the Fugaku server which achieves 537.21 Petaflops of peak performance, and from June 2020 until June of 2022 was ranked number 1 on top500, until it was superseded by frontier. ⁴ ⁵

¹<https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/1febbbb2c4fd4b7d92c67ddd353b6ae8/en-gb/pdfs/ki-strategi.en.pdf>

²<https://www.olcf.ornl.gov/frontier/>

³<https://www.top500.org/lists/top500/2023/11/>

⁴https://abci.ai/en/about_abci/computing_resource.html

⁵<https://www.r-ccs.riken.jp/en/fugaku/about/>

4.1.3 EU

The EU and their partners has invested heavily into compute resources, with 3 servers currently on the scale of more than 300 Petaflops, of which LUMI is currently ranked number 5 in the world on top 500, with 531.51 Petaflops of compute. On top of this they are currently investing in an exascale supercomputer, to be installed in Germany during 2024. Leading the EU with their other nation and private sector partners to currently holding 1.222 Exaflops in total compute among 8 servers, with more than one additional exaflop to be installed in 2024. ⁶

4.2 National Compute for AI in Norway

⁷ In Norway, as of July 2024, we have the National Research Infrastructure Service (NRIS), along with each institution's separate computing resources. With NRIS hosting approximately 8.1 Petaflops of compute ⁸. When we look at each institution in NAIC we find that the compute resources varies quite a lot, with the most prominent problem from the survey takers being compute resources.

4.3 Current use

- 8x Nvidia 1080ti - 0.355TFlops
- 16x Nvidia 2080ti - 0.420TFlops
- 20x Nvidia 3090 - 0.638TFlops
- 4x Nvidia A6000 - 19.6TFlops
- 144x Nvidia V100 32GB - 7TFlops
- 4x Nvidia V100 16GB - 7TFlops
- 23x Nvidia P100 16GB - 4.7TFlops
- 23x Nvidia A100 80GB - 9.7TFlops
- 36x Nvidia A100 40GB - 9.7TFlops
- 24x Nvidia H100 80GB - 24TFlops (PCIe)/ 30 (SXM)

⁶https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/supercomputers/our-supercomputers_en

⁷<https://documentation.sigma2.no/>

⁸https://documentation.sigma2.no/hpc_machines/hardware_overview.html#hardware-overview

- 2x Nvidia T4 16GB - 4.1TFlops
- 6x Nvidia P40 24GB - 6TFlops

The NAIC partners have a total of 10.427 PFlops - Theoretical max peak. Compared to 37888 Radeon Instinct MI250x - 47.9TFlops, resulting in 1814.83 PFlops Theoretical max peak. Which is 174.05 times more than the compute available to the institutions in NAIC.

4.4 Future needs

As Norway wishes to compete on an international stage with respect to its AI development, large amounts of AI need to be available. These computing resources need to be enough that researchers and developers from all over Norway have the ability to create more complex and innovative AI. This leads to more GPU resources, good queuing solutions, as well as software for distributing code across multiple physical servers.

5 Data

Large-scale compute resources are required for AI, but for many AI tasks so is a reliable, secure storage solution. While having access to such a solution would allow for faster prototyping of AI algorithms which use sensitive data, a lack of one can lead to a lack of development in the field the data is on. Meaning that though someone has the computing resources to train a model, if they cannot find a reliable, fast and secure storage solution, they are unable to train the model.

5.1 Current use

Currently there are multiple such solution around, which includes the JASMIN solution for climate and earth science applications, GÉANT, which is the pan-European solution, and the UK Research Data Facility (RDF). As for Norway UiO has their TSD services, and the Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services (NRIS) NIRD solution for the partners of NRIS. While TSD allows for the storage of sensitive data, up to level black, NIRD allows for storage of to level green and yellow. As for other institutions they need to develop their own systems.

5.2 Barriers to access

There are a few different barriers to access the storage solutions currently, access to sufficient storage resources, strict enough access given the requested permissions for the data, delay, availability, and cost to developed a solution for each institution. Though universities like UiO currently has a storage solution with permissions for sensitive data, this is not the case for each institution. Not only does each institution need to pay for storage, they also need to develop a similar solution as UiO, or pay for access. While paying for access is possible, it is likely more expensive in the long term.

5.3 Future needs

As we gather more and more data, we require more and more storage. Future needs not only necessitate more storage capacity but also the ability to handle more users at once, as well as faster transfer speeds. Current technology would make the streaming of Terabytes of data at once slow, which may exclude some AI tasks, such as developing a climate data model.

Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC) is aiming to fix this, by setting up a storage solution in which a user uploads the data in one location and is able to access it with multiple other servers connected to the storage solution. NAICs solution aims to provide consolidated access to distributed data and local read-only data caches near compute. It also aims at increased robustness in data availability that could improve total uptime. This lower delay could lead to significantly faster training of algorithms, which in turn means less downtime and more utilization of the resources currently available.

6 Conclusion

As part Work package 2 of the NAIC project, we created two surveys which had 78 respondents in total. The survey gathered information on the respondents, their backgrounds, institutions, computing and storage resources, and workflows when developing AI algorithms. Among the responses, we found that the majority of users use Python, with two other large groups using C++ and R as their programming language. The majority of users also use GPU for their computing needs, of which a majority of respondents said they use NVIDIA GPUs with CUDA. There were a few evident problems that the users had, namely that there was either a lack of compute resources, or a lack of knowledge of how to use them most efficiently. Due to 42 percent of respondents in the first survey being from UiO, with a large part of the remaining respondents being in academia, there was a bias towards universities and in particular UiO.

To fill any knowledge gap from the survey, a set of interviews were done. The interviewees were chosen based on their field of research, while also attempting to get as many industry members to respond as possible. The results here did not differ much from what the survey told us, with compute resources being the largest problem, as well there was also an issue which revolved around training AI models using vast amounts of data.

A secondary survey was conducted to try to rule out any bias appearing due to the overwhelming responses from the academic sector in the first survey. The results did not differ much from our first run and the interview round, with the biggest exception being that a larger percentage of new respondents were using or wanting to use cloud solutions compared to the previous survey.

When we compare the compute resources on the institutions in NAIC to the most powerful American supercomputer, namely Frontier, we find that though Norway has approximately 1/60th the number of people it only seems to have approximately 1/174th the amount of compute.

As for the lack of data storage solutions, we found that there are some storage solutions hosted through NRIS and by UiO, however some institutions have to rent data storage servers, and may be unable to use another institutions data storage solution for specific projects. The problem could arise from streaming vast amounts of data, or data privacy. When streaming data, the problem is the internet speed and the data pipeline from the storage solutions are required to be able to send PetaBytes of data rapidly, for example when developing a climate model. As for the data privacy, only TSD is able to store up to black

level data.